

Polarographic Study of Mixed-ligand Complexes of Cadmium(II) with L-Amino Acid and Vitamin B₅

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A survey of literature shows that ternary complexes of Cd^{II} with L-amino acids and vitamin B₅ have not been studied so far. The present communication reports the formation of mixed-ligand complexes of Cd^{II} with L-amino acids as primary ligands and vitamin B₅ as secondary ligand, studied by polarographic technique.

Results and Discussion

Cd^{II} gives a well-defined reversible reduction and diffusion controlled wave at constant ionic strength ($\mu = 1.0 M KNO_3$), pH (8.50 \pm 0.01) and temperature (25°). The ratio of ligands were 1 : 40 for binary complexes and 1 : 40 : 40 for ternary complexes. Initially C-V curve were plotted at different pH of the solutions. The maximum shift in $E_{1/2}$ was observed at pH = 8.50 \pm 0.01.

Cd^{II}-vitamin B₅ system : A single wave was observed in each case at constant ionic strength ($\mu = 1.0 M KNO_3$) and at pH = 8.50 \pm 0.01 and 25°. Stability constants of 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 Cd^{II} complexes with vitamin B₅ were calculated by Lingane's method¹. The concentration of vitamin B₅ varied from 10 mM to 100 mM. The values of stability constant are given in Table 1.

Cd^{II}-L-Amino acidate-vitamin B₅ system : Ternary systems were studied at constant concentrations of vitamin B₅ (viz. 0.025 and 0.050 M) and varying the concentration of primary ligand from 0.5 to 50 mM and C-V curves were drawn. In each case well-defined reversible and diffusion-controlled wave was obtained. $E_{1/2}$ shifted to a more nega-

tive side on increasing concentration of ligand. The formation of 1:1:1, 1:1:2 and 1:2:1 complexes were confirmed by Schaap and McMaster method². Table 1 presents the values of stability constant of ternary complexes. The polarographic characteristics and $F_{ij} [X, Y]$ values of Cd^{II}-L-lysine-vitamin B₅ system are presented in Table 2.

The values of mixing constants ($\log K_m$) used to compare the stability of binary and ternary complexes were calculated by the equation,

$$\log K_m = \log \beta_{11} - 1/2 (\log \beta_{20} + \log \beta_{02})$$

which are -0.34, -0.245, -0.35, -0.255, -0.220, -0.125, -0.125 and -0.030 for [Cd-L-lys-vitamin B₅], [Cd-L-orn.-vitamin B₅], [Cd-L-threo.-vitamin B₅], [Cd-L-ser.-vitamin B₅], [Cd-L-phenylgly.-vitamin B₅], [Cd-L-phenylala.-vitamin B₅], [Cd-L-glut.-vitamin B₅], [Cd-L-asp.-vitamin B₅] system respectively. The values of $\log K_m$ obtained are negative, showing that the ternary complexes are less stable than the binary complexes. The order of stability constant was L-lys. < L-orn. < L-threo. < L-ser. < L-phenylgly. < L-phenylala. < L-glu. < L-asp.

The stability of L-lysinate complexes is minimum owing to the pK values of L-lysine; as pK value increases the stability of complexes increases³. L-Threoninate complexes are less stable than L-serinate. This is attributed to the fact that the electron-withdrawing OH group is closer to the metal in the former, thus effecting greater repulsive forces between OH group and metal ions in L-threoninate com-

TABLE 1—pK VALUES AND STABILITY CONSTANTS* OF TERNARY COMPLEXES OF Cd^{II} WITH L-AMINO ACIDS AND NICOTINIC ACID (VITAMIN B₅)
 $\mu = 1.0 M (KNO_3)$, pH = 8.50 \pm 0.01, temp. = 25°

Ligand	pK ₂ ^H	log β_{01}	log β_{02}	log β_{10}	log β_{20}	log β_{30}	log β_{11}	log β_{12}	log β_{21}
L-Lysine	8.95	—	—	3.70	6.48	9.24	4.00	6.60	9.30
L-Ornithine	8.98	—	—	3.77	6.61	9.42	4.16	6.825	9.525
L-Threonine	9.00	—	—	4.00	7.00	9.50	4.25	6.88	9.72
L-Serine	9.20	—	—	4.07	7.13	9.69	4.41	7.10	9.945
L-Phenylglycine	9.23	—	—	4.10	7.24	9.71	4.50	7.32	9.98
L-Phenylalanine	9.30	—	—	4.17	7.37	9.90	4.66	7.54	10.205
L-Glutamic acid	9.67	—	—	4.30	7.45	10.06	4.70	7.60	10.30
L-Aspartic acid	9.82	—	—	4.37	7.58	10.24	4.86	7.825	10.525
Vitamin B ₅	—	1.40	2.20	—	—	—	—	—	—

*Original values upto 4th decimal place.

TABLE 2—POLAROGRAPHIC CHARACTERISTICS AND $F_{ij}[X,Y]$ VALUES OF Cd^{II} -L-LYSINE-VITAMIN B_5 SYSTEM[Cd^{II}] = 0.5 mM, μ = 1.0 M (KNO_3), pH = 8.50 \pm 0.01, temp. = 25°[Vitamin B_5] = 0.025 M (fixed)

(L-lys.) M	$E_{1/2}$ V	$\log I_m/I_c$	$F_{00}(X,Y)$	$F_{10}(X,Y)$ $\times 10^{-3}$	$F_{20}(X,Y)$ $\times 10^{-6}$	$F_{30}(X,Y)$ $\times 10^{-8}$
0.000	—	—	—	—	—	—
0.0005	0.03738	0.0144	19.041	34.629	53.758	17.37
0.001	0.05296	0.0144	64.105	62.379	54.629	17.39
0.002	0.06983	0.0219	242.762	120.518	56.538	17.42
0.003	0.08028	0.0219	547.831	182.035	58.095	17.35
0.004	0.08765	0.0294	990.006	247.070	59.830	17.35
0.005	0.09365	0.0294	1579.851	315.625	61.575	17.37
0.006	0.09862	0.0294	2327.458	387.622	63.312	17.37
0.008	0.10639	0.0371	4340.078	542.294	66.818	17.41
0.010	0.11247	0.0449	7100.226	709.850	70.210	17.34
0.020	0.13302	0.0449	35208.726	1760.350	87.63	17.37
0.030	0.14549	0.0529	94761.226	3158.650	105.030	17.38
0.040	0.1545	0.0610	196103.72	4902.550	122.370	17.37
0.050	0.1620	0.0610	349789.226	6204.750	139.740	17.37
log A = 0.2372		log B = 3.8893	log C = 7.7233	log D = 9.2390		

plexes than in L-serinate complexes. L-Phenylglycinate complexes are more stable than those of L-serinate and L-threoninate complexes. This can be explained on the basis of H-bond formation between OH and amino group in L-serinate and L-threoninate complexes resulting in the lesser stability of their complexes than L-phenylalanine and L-phenylglycine. L-Glutamate complexes are less stable than L-aspartate complexes which might be a result of ring size, as the L-glutamate formed five- and seven-membered rings whereas L-aspartate five- and six-membered rings in complex formation⁴. As the ring size increases the stability of complexes decreases³. The stabilities of the L-glutamate, and L-aspartate complexes are greater than those of L-lysinate, L-ornithinate, L-threoninate, L-serinate, L-phenylglycinate, L-phenylalaninate as a result of large difference in their basic strengths.

Experimental

Solutions were prepared in double-distilled water. The purity of L-amino acids was checked by chromatographic method⁵. Ionic strength was maintained constant at μ = 1.0 M using KNO_3 . The concentration of metal (0.5 mM) was kept constant. Test solutions were deoxygenated by passing pure hydrogen before C-V curve was recorded⁶.

A manual polarograph using Toshniwal PL-50 galvanometer was used to record C-V curves. An Elico L-I-120 pH meter was used. Saturated calomel electrode was used as a reference electrode. The capillary characteristic of the electrode was $m^{2/3}t^{1/6} = 2.40 \text{ mg}^{2/3} \text{ s}^{-1/2}$ at mercury height of 60.02 cm.

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